

DISTRIBUTION OF SOME EUROPEAN LEPIDOPTERA BASED ON THE FINDINGS OF THEIR NON-ADULT STAGES PRESENTED THROUGH TROPHIC ASSOCIATIONS AND A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF THEIR PARASITIDS

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Abstract

We examined 638 Lepidoptera specimens on the territories of 13 European countries in our search for parasitoids. We collected eggs, larvae and pupae. In total, 251 Lepidoptera species were identified, belonging to 169 genera from 30 families. Of the total sample, approximately one-third (32.23%) were parasitized. In 168 samples (26.42%), we identified only one parasitoid species per host. In addition to these data, 224 plant species from 114 genera were identified, of which the vast majority were feeding plants.

KEY WORDS: diversity, Lepidoptera, eggs, caterpillars, pupae, feeding plants, parasitoids

Introduction

There are approximately 157,761 lepidopteran species described in world fauna and they are classified into 131 families (Goldstein, 2017). According to the online data base Lepiforum (<http://www.lepiforum.de>), 10,543 species from 27 families are found in Europe. Although there are some studies regarding the diversity and spatial distribution of certain Lepidoptera species that are recorded as being present in a particular territory, there are errors. Some species were only occasionally found in the studied fauna although they do not actually develop in the specified area, regardless of the presence of host plants for their larvae or limiting climatic conditions. Such cases usually suggest that the species have been wrongly identified but could also be a result of the introduction of insects carried by the wind or through various human activities, such as transportation. One such example is the pine processionary moth, *Thaumetopoea pityocampa* (Denis & Schiffermüller) (Notodontidae), which was reported in central Serbia after the collection of several adults in light traps (Glavendekić, 2010; Glavendekić & Mihajlović, 2012). After that, the pine processionary moth was not recorded either by checking typically made caterpillar nests or by setting pheromone traps during 2016-2018 (personal work). Previous incidental findings leave the possibility that adults may have been transferred by wind to another territory. The second case was a single adult specimen of *Utetheisa pulchella* (L.) (Erebidae), collected with a light trap in the north of Serbia (Vajgand, 2012). Another good example is *Polyommatus escheri* Hübner, which was recorded in Serbia in various places far from its host plant (Popović & Verovnik, 2018).

The intention of the authors was to present an assemblage of numerous data on caterpillar samples collected on feeding plants. Originally, caterpillars were collected for rearing in laboratories in order to obtain parasitoids for trophic-chain investigations. We believe that the material is worth sharing with the scientific community, as it was collected over a period of 30 years and contains a vast amount of data on caterpillars, their feeding plants, as well as their parasitoids. Such a massive exploration of non-adult diversity in the field has never been published before, especially for the eastern European region.

Materials and Methods

Different stages of Lepidoptera, mainly larvae, were sampled together with their feeding plants. Some of the plants were herbarized and identified by a botanist, while the remainder was used to feed the caterpillars. Sampling was carried out in 13 European countries, predominantly in eastern Europe (Fig. 1). The material was collected over a period of 30 years, from 1989 to 2019. For most of the individuals, photographs were taken and sent to experts for identification. A large number of caterpillars, as well as eggs and chrysalides, were grown in laboratory conditions, anticipating parasitoids in the case they were previously parasitized, or until death of the caterpillars or the emergence of lepidopteran imagoes. In these cases, we provided data on whether the individuals were parasitized, and the number of parasitoid species that emerged from them.

Abbreviations of legators: AN = A. Nahirić, AP = A. Petrović, BH = B. Hric, DD = D. Djordjević, DM = D. Marczak, H-PT = H-P. Tschorsnig, KK = K. Kos, ML = M. Lazarević, MIM = M. Ilić Milošević, MR = M. Ristić, NK = N. Kavallieratos, NKD = N. Kisić Dedić, NV = N. Veljković, OMI = Óscar Moreno Iriondo, PJ = P. Jakšić, SS = S. Stanković, SST = S. Stevčić, ŠM = Š. Modić, VŽ = V. Žikić, YML = Y. M. León, ŽT = Ž. Tomanović, [only initials: JF, ŽP, LV, LM, MK, AH, GU, JR, ST, TB, MV].

Results

The largest number of specimens is from Serbia (467), followed by samples from Greece (47), Slovenia (47), Montenegro (37), Poland (14), Spain (9), Austria (5), Croatia (4), Bulgaria (4), with one specimen each from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Italy, Sweden and UK (Table A1, Fig. 1). Summarizing all the findings, the total number of examined samples was 638. The number of registered lepidopterans was 251 species belonging to 169 genera from 30 families. We identified 224 plant species from 114 genera, of which the vast majority were feeding plants. Cases where caterpillars were found on plants that are not recorded in their diet menu are marked with an asterisk (*) in Table A1. The number of plant families was 47. Most of the samples were collected from plants of the Rosaceae family (134) with 14 genera and 33 species, followed by the Asteraceae family with 8 genera and 13 species and the Fabaceae family with 12 genera and 20 species.

Figure 1. Number of samples collected per country.

Eighty-six lepidopteran species were not found on feeding plants but on the ground or on bark, such as *Agrotis segetum* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775), *Thalpothila matura* (Hufnagel, 1766), in beehives – *Galleria mellonella* (Linnaeus, 1758), as well as in stored products and grains – *Plodia interpunctella* (Hübner, 1813). The vast majority of caterpillars were found as mature larvae in their final (L5) instar. In some cases, for the same species, all larval instars (L1-L5) and even pupae, were found, e.g., *Lymantria dispar* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Malacosoma neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Saturnia pavoniella* (Scopoli, 1763), *Thaumetopoea pityocampa* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775), or all four species from the genus *Yponomeuta*.

Figure 2. Number of parasitoid species collected per host displayed in percentage.

About two-thirds of the analyzed samples (67.77%) were either not parasitized or the hosts died before the parasitoids could leave their bodies (Fig. 2). In 205 cases, the larval or other stages were parasitized. The number in the last column in Table A1 shows the exact number of parasitoid species recorded, including primary and secondary parasitoids. This information refers to both hymenopteran (various superfamilies and families) and dipteran (fam. Tachinidae) species. For the vast majority of hosts (26.42%; 168 samples) we registered only one parasitoid species per host, or 2 parasitoids per host (3.77%; 24 samples). In 6 cases we found 3 different parasitoid species, such as in *Pleuroptya ruralis* (Scopoli, 1763), a species frequently found on common nettle. In the case of *Yponomeuta cagnagella* (Hübner, 1813), we identified 4 parasitoid species and 5 per the following lepidopterans: *Heterogynis zikici* de Freina 2018; *Y. malinellus* (Zeller, 1838) and *Y. padella* (Linnaeus 1758). The olive moth, *Prays oleae* (Bernard, 1788) was found to be parasitized with 6 parasitoid species. The most parasitoid species (8) were found in *Zygaena filipendulae* (Linnaeus 1758).

Discussion

Although most of the Lepidoptera samples were collected primarily in the search for their parasitoids, we used the opportunity to contribute to the knowledge about butterfly and moth fauna for the investigated territories. There is a strong need to collect precise data on lepidopterans in their immature stages, since this contributes to an understanding of their ecology and can help in removing these species from the checklist of a region in which they do not breed, i.e., they are not native on the investigated territory. Following new trends in systematics and phylogeny, we tried to present as accurately as possible the systematics of Lepidoptera we analyzed and commented on. Nowadays the availability of molecular analyses, and in particular the use of the barcoding sequence of cytochrome oxidase 1 (COI), sheds new light on taxonomy,

resulting in changes in the taxonomic status and/or names of many taxa. These changes elucidate trophic associations, the number of host plants per lepidopteran species and also the parasitoid spectrum.

In analyzing Table A1, it is noticeable that the gypsy moth *Lymantria dispar* and the lackey moth *Malacosoma neustria* occur in outbreaks. In Serbia, an outbreak of the gypsy moth occurred in 2013 and in Greece in 2016. An outbreak of the lackey moth was registered in the territory of Greece in 2016, where it was in direct competition with the gypsy moth (Žikić *et al.*, 2017).

We wish to point out that in addition to the 638 samples and 251 lepidopteran species presented here, we also collected and photographed more than 400 individuals that are as yet unidentified (currently identified to the family level). A large number of unidentified caterpillars belong to the group of "Microlepidoptera", in particular, twirler moths (Gelechiidae), blotch leaf miner moths (Gracillariidae), diamond-back moths (Plutellidae) and many more. We hope that once they are identified by experts, data will be published in forthcoming papers. For future studies, it may also be important to resolve whether unknown host plants recorded for some lepidopterans are new in their diet, and if not, provide definitive confirmation of accidental finding.

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ДИСТРИБУЦИЈА НЕКИХ ЕВРОПСКИХ LEPIDOPTERA НА ОСНОВУ ПРОНАЛАСКА НЕАДУЛТНИХ СТАДИЈУМА ПРЕДСТАВЉЕНА ПРЕКО ТРОФИЧКИХ АСОЦИЈАЦИЈА И КВАНТИТАТИВНА АНАЛИЗА ЊИХОВИХ ПАРАЗИТОИДА

ВЛАДИМИР ЖИКИЋ, РУДОЛФ РИТ, МАРКО КОЛАЋИ, БОЖЕНКА ХРИЦ, САША С. СТАНКОВИЋ,
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МОНАСТЕРИО ЛЕОН, МИХАИЛО ВУЛИЋ, РОМАН МАГЛИЋ И ЈОСЕФ ДЕ ФРЕИНА

Извод

Истражили смо 638 узорак Lepidoptera у потрази за паразитоидима на територији 13 европских земаља. Сакупљали смо јаја, ларве и лутке. Идентификована је укупно 251 врста лептира из 169 родова и 30 фамилија. Од укупног узорка, 32,23% узорак је било паразитирано, што је приближно једна трећина. У 168 узорак (26,42%) идентификовали смо једну врсту паразитоида по домаћину. Такође, 224 врсте биљака из 114 родова је идентификовано од тога већина хранитељки.

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Appendix

Table A1. List of lepidopteran and host plants specimens. Abbreviations for stage / larval instar from which the parasitoid emerged: O – egg stage; L – larval stage; P – pupal stage, A – adult stage; (1-5) – larval instars; * – uncertain host plant.

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Choreutidae	<i>Anthophila fabriciana</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Brzi brod, 18.10.2018, SST	L5	-
Choreutidae	<i>Choreutis nemorana</i> (Hübner, 1799)	Moraceae	<i>Ficus carica</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 10.08.2017, VŽ	L4-5	2
Choreutidae	<i>Choreutis nemorana</i> (Hübner, 1799)	Moraceae	<i>Ficus carica</i>	SERBIA, Knjaževac 25.09.2018, VŽ	P	-
Coleophoridae	<i>Coleophora vibicella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Crambidae	<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> (Walker, 1859)	Buxaceae	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 10.08.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Crambidae	<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> (Walker, 1859)	Buxaceae	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L4-5, P	-
Crambidae	<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> (Walker, 1859)	Buxaceae	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 13.09.2016, VŽ	L1-5	-
Crambidae	<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> (Walker, 1859)	Buxaceae	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Palilula, 12.07.2016, VŽ	L1-5	-
Crambidae	<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> (Walker, 1859)	Buxaceae	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 10.07.2017, VŽ	L1-5	-
Crambidae	<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	SLOVENIA, Jablje, 03.09.2011, JR & ŠM	L5	1
Crambidae	<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	SLOVENIA, Rakičan, 21.09.2012, AH & GU	L5	1
Crambidae	<i>Pleuroptya ruralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Crambidae	<i>Pleuroptya ruralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura (gorge), 14.05.2013, VŽ	L4-5	3
Crambidae	<i>Pleuroptya ruralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L5	1
Crambidae	<i>Pleuroptya ruralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 10.06.2017, VŽ	L5	2
Crambidae	<i>Pleuroptya ruralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, Ostroviča, 10.05.2016, SS	L5	3
Depressariidae	<i>Agonoapterix ocellana</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Plavsko jezero, Gusinje, 12.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Depressariidae	<i>Depressaria chaerophylli</i> Zeller, 1839	Apiaceae	<i>Chaerophyllum bulbosum</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 13.07.2013, VŽ	L3	-
Drepanidae	<i>Asphalia ruficollis</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Amata phegea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asteraceae	<i>Crepis foetida</i> *	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Amata phegea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolatum</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 13.04.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Amata phegea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 21.04.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Apopestes spectrum</i> (Esper, 1787)	Fabaceae	<i>Spartium junceum</i>	MONTENEGRO, Budva, 25.05.2010., VŽ	L5	2
Erebidae	<i>Apopestes spectrum</i> (Esper, 1787)	Fabaceae	<i>Spartium junceum</i>	MONTENEGRO, Bečići, 18.05.2011, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Erebidae	<i>Arctia caja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	CROATIA, Plitvice (lake), 29.06.2015, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Arctia caja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	MONTENEGRO, Durmitor, Mali Meded, 09.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Arctia caja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Arctia caja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asteraceae	<i>Hieracium pilosella</i> *	SERBIA, Kopaonik mt., 05.07.2010, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Arctia caja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> *	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m, 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Arctia villica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 06.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Arctia villica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Arctornis l-nigrum</i> (Müller, 1764)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera caprifolium</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Calliteara pudibunda</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Prokuplje, 05.10.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Calyptra thalictri</i> (Borkhausen, 1790)	Ranunculaceae	<i>Thalictrum aquilegifolium</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac, 27.06.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Calyptra thalictri</i> (Borkhausen, 1790)	Ranunculaceae	<i>Thalictrum minus</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 31.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Calyptra thalictri</i> (Borkhausen, 1790)	Ranunculaceae	<i>Thalictrum minus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 16.06.2009, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Coleophora vibicella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 17.06.2013, VŽ	L5	2
Erebidae	<i>Coscinia striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Kamenički vis, 02.05.2017, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Coscinia striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Coscinia striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Festuca</i> sp.	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 19.06.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Diacrisia purpurata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 08.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Diacrisia sannio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Zlatibor, Čavlovac, 28.06.2018, ML	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Diaphora mendica</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš Gornji Matejevac 21.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Dicallomera fascelina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 26.05.2016, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Dicallomera fascelina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 16.06.2013, VŽ	L3-4	-
Erebidae	<i>Dysauxes punctata</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> sp.	Spain, León, Valdeón, 1260m, 07.08.2018, YML	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Eilema complana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	MONTENEGRO, Durmitor, Pištavine, 09.07.2013, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Eilema complana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus carpiniifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 25.05.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Euplagia quadripunctaria</i> (Poda, 1761)	Boraginaceae	<i>Anchusa officinalis</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Euproctis similis</i> (Füssli, 1775)	/	/	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, Truskaw, 21.06.2018, DM	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Erebidae	<i>Euproctis similis</i> (Füssli, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa x hybrida</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Stevan Sindelić, 02.09.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Euproctis similis</i> (Füssli, 1775)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 11.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Laspeyresia servillana</i> (Duponchel, 1836)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix alba</i>	SLOVENIA, Vipava, Dragonja, 1989, JF	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Laspeyresia servillana</i> (Duponchel, 1836)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SLOVENIA, Horjul, 1989, JF	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Laspeyresia servillana</i> (Duponchel, 1836)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix purpurea</i>	SLOVENIA, Polhov Gradec, 1989, JF	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Leucoma salicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Kopaonik mt., 19.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Leucoma salicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 08.06.2014, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Anacardiaceae	<i>Cotinus coggygria</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	2
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Anacardiaceae	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cistaceae	<i>Cistus creticus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Carpinus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 12.05.2013., VŽ	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>	SERBIA, Tara, Derвента 25.06.2013., VŽ	L3-4	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>	SERBIA, Tara, Derвента 25.06.2013., VŽ	L3-4	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., 25.06.2016, VŽ	L4	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ericaceae	<i>Arbutus andrachne</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, SS	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ericaceae	<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus coccifera</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	3
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus coccifera</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus robur</i>	SERBIA, Sokobanja, Bovansko jezero (lake) 10.05.2005, VŽ	L3-4	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus ornus*</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oleaceae	<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Pinaceae	<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rhamnaceae	<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura 15.05.2013, VŽ	L4	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Konjino 15.05.2012, SS	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Sokobanja, Bovansko jezero (lake) 14.06.2008, VŽ	L4	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus spinosa</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus hirtus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L3-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus alba</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 12.05.2013., VŽ	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus nigra</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge) 19.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Pištaline, 09.07.2013, VŽ	L4	2
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus canescens</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 12.05.2013., VŽ	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 12.05.2013., VŽ	L2	1
Erebidae	<i>Lymantria dispar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Viburnaceae	<i>Viburnum opulus</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, VŽ	L2-5	1
Erebidae	<i>Ocneria terebinthi</i> (Freyer, 1838)	Anacardiaceae	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Ocnogyna baetica</i> (Rambur, 1836)	Malvaceae	<i>Malva sylvestris</i>	Spain, Jaen, Las Lagunillas, 04.03.2005, YML	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Orgyia antiqua</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m. a.s.l., 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	/	/	SERBIA, Prokuplje, Gornja Konjuša 01.05.2016 MR	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 22.05.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii*</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 16.06.2013, VŽ	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Poaceae	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Poaceae	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L2-5	1
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Poaceae	<i>Lolium perene</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.05.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Penthophera morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Poaceae	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 14.04.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Erebidae	<i>Phragmatobia fuliginosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Matejevac, 18.10.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Rhyparia purpurata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Kruševac, Donji Stepoš, 01.05.2016, ML	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Rhyparia purpurata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Erebidae	<i>Setina roscida</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	/	MONTENEGRO, Pištaline 09.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Spiris striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Erebidae	<i>Spirisstriata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L4	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis aurantaria</i> (Hübner, 1799)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis bajaria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera nigra</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 14.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis bajaria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis bajaria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis bajaria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 10.05.2015, VŽ	L3-4	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis leucophaearia</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Agriopsis marginaria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L4	-
Geometridae	<i>Alsophila aceraria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Alsophila aescularia</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera caprifolium</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Alsophila aescularia</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Alsophila aescularia</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac 10.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Alsophila aescularia</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Anticlea derivata</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	MONTENEGRO, Gusinje, 12.07.2013, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Anticlea derivata</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa tomentosa</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m, 13.07.2013, VŽ	L4	-
Geometridae	<i>Artiora evonymaria</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus europaeus</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), Sićevo, 01.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Biston betularia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Betulaceae	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	MONTENEGRO, Tara canyon, Tepce, 13.07.2013, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Biston strataria</i> (Hufnagel, 1767)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 11.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Anacardiaceae	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera caprifolium</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera caprifolium</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, SST & VŽ	L4	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Juglandaceae	<i>Juglans regia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS & VŽ	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Oleaceae	<i>Syringa vulgaris</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 13.05.2015, VŽ	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Colotois pennaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Cyclophora punctaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus robur</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, SS	L4	-
Geometridae	<i>Earophila badiata</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 20.05.2015, ML	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Ectropis crepuscularia</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rhamnaceae	<i>Frangula alnus</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, VŽ	L3, L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Ennomos quercinaria</i> (Hufnagel, 1767)	Corylaceae	<i>Carpinus orientalis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 24.05.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Panteleji, 14.04.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	/	Poaceae*	MONTENEGRO, Plavsko jezero, Gusinje, 12.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Corylaceae	<i>Carpinus orientalis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 20.05.2015, ML	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Corylaceae	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L3-5	1
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Juglandaceae	<i>Juglans regia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Malvaceae	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 04.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L3	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus avium</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt. 10.05.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L3-4	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L3-5	1
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 12.05.2015, VŽ	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 12.05.2015, VŽ	L3-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Erannis defoliaria</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer negundo</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Lycia alpina</i> (Sulzer, 1776)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 01.08.2015, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Geometridae	<i>Lycia graecarius</i> (Staudinger, 1861)	Asteraceae	<i>Crepis foetida</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., 25.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Lycia graecarius</i> (Staudinger, 1861)	Berberidaceae	<i>Berberis</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 12.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Lycia graecarius</i> (Staudinger, 1861)	Fabaceae	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 10.06.2017, SS	L4	-
Geometridae	<i>Lycia graecarius</i> (Staudinger, 1861)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., Derventa canyon, 25.06.2015, SS	L4-5	-
Geometridae	<i>Operophtera brumata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Juglandaceae	<i>Juglans regia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Operophtera brumata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Operophtera brumata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, ML	L5	-
Geometridae	<i>Orthostixis cribraria</i> (Hübner, 1799)	Lamiaceae	<i>Scutellaria altissima</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L3-5	1
Geometridae	<i>Orthostixis cribraria</i> (Hübner, 1799)	Lamiaceae	<i>Scutellaria altissima</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, VŽ	L3-4	-
Geometridae	<i>Peribatodes rhomboidaria</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera</i> sp.*	GREECE, Athens, Botanical Garden, 06.05.2016, VŽ	L5	2
Geometridae	<i>Phigalia pilosaria</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	1
Geometridae	<i>Phigalia pilosaria</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L3-5	1
Geometridae	<i>Phigalia pilosaria</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer negundo</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Gracillariidae	<i>Cameraria ohridella</i> (Deschka & Dimic 1986)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	POLAND, Warszawa, Łazienki Królewskie, 03.06.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Gracillariidae	<i>Cameraria ohridella</i> (Deschka & Dimic 1986)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 18.06.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Gracillariidae	<i>Cameraria ohridella</i> (Deschka & Dimic 1986)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., 25.06.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Gracillariidae	<i>Cameraria ohridella</i> (Deschka & Dimic 1986)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	SLOVENIA, Lipica, 2003 LV & MK	L5	1
Gracillariidae	<i>Cameraria ohridella</i> (Deschka & Dimic 1986)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, 2006, KK & LM	L5	1
Heliozelidae	<i>Heliozela betulae</i> (Stainton, 1890)	Betulaceae	<i>Betula pendula</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, 1989, JF	L5	-
Heliozelidae	<i>Heliozela resplendella</i> (Stainton 1851)	Betulaceae	<i>Alnus incana</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, 1989, JF	L5	-
Heliozelidae	<i>Heliozela sericiella</i> (Haworth, 1828)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SLOVENIA, Pivka, 1989, JF	L5	-
Heliozelidae	<i>Heliozela sericiella</i> (Haworth, 1828)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	SLOVENIA, Dobrna, 1989, JF	L5	-
Heliozelidae	<i>Heliozela sericiella</i> (Haworth, 1828)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	SLOVENIA, Planina pri Ajdovščini, 1989, JF	L5	-
Heliozelidae	<i>Heliozela sericiella</i> (Haworth, 1828)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus robur</i>	SLOVENIA, Ivanjkovci, 1989, JF	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Hesperiidae	<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, 1780)	Malvaceae	<i>Alcea rosea</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Doljevac 23.09.2018, VŽ	L3-5	1
Hesperiidae	<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, 1780)	Malvaceae	<i>Alcea rosea</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej 18.09.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Hesperiidae	<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, 1780)	Malvaceae	<i>Alcea rosea</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, Građy, 27.06.2018, DM	L5	2
Hesperiidae	<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, 1780)	Malvaceae	<i>Alcea rosea</i>	SERBIA, Subotica, Selevenjska pustara, 10.08.2015. MP	L5	1
Hesperiidae	<i>Carcharodus baeticus</i> (Rambur, 1839)	Lamiaceae	<i>Ballota</i> sp.	SPAIN, Navarra, Pitillas, 01.06.2015, YML	L5	2
Hesperiidae	<i>Muschampia proto</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	Lamiaceae	<i>Phlomis lychnitis</i>	SPAIN, El Cortijo, Logroño, La Rioja, 01.04.2017, YML	L5	-
Heterogynidae	<i>Heterogynis zikici</i> de Freina 2018	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 16.06.2013, VŽ	L5	3
Heterogynidae	<i>Heterogynis zikici</i> de Freina 2018	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecytisus heuffelii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	5
Lasiocampidae	<i>Dendrolimus pini</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Pinaceae	<i>Pinus nigra</i>	MONTENEGRO, Bijelo Polje 25.05.2011, AP	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster catax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SPAIN, Medrano, La Rioja, 01.04.2017, YML	L5	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster catax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster catax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rhamnaceae	<i>Paliurus spinachristi</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster catax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster catax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 09.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster catax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster lanestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Paraćin 08.05.2018 NV	L5	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster lanestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 08.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster lanestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura (gorge), 05.05.2014, PJ	L2	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster lanestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura, Gradište, 19.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster lanestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L1-2	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Eriogaster rnicola</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Euthrix potatoria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cyperaceae	<i>Carex</i> sp.	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, SS	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	MONTENEGRO, Pištaline, 09.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 23.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Genista tinctoria</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor, Čavlovac, 28.06.2018, ML	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Paraćin, 06.05.2018, NV	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., 25.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa trifolii</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa trifolii</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Sičevaka klisura (gorge), 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa trifolii</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Tara mt., 25.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa trifolii</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Pčinja canyon, 14.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Lasiocampa trifolii</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac 27.06.2015, MIM	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Zlatibor, Čavlovac, 28.06.2018, ML	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ericaceae	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 13.07.2013, VŽ	L2	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 10.06.2017, SS	L2	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 12.06.2016, VŽ	L2-3	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 30.09.2018, IS	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Poa</i> sp.	MONTENEGRO, Plavsko jezero, Gusinje, 12.07.2013, VŽ	L2-3	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Festuca</i> sp.	BULGARIA, Rila mt. 7 lakes, 2500 m a.s.l., 23.07.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Macrothylacia rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Festuca</i> sp.	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 28.02.017, VŽ	L2-3	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma castrensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea</i> sp.*	CROATIA, Plitvice (lake), 22.06.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma castrensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Berberidaceae	<i>Berberis vulgaris</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Brassicaceae	<i>Lepidium draba</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Ostryia carpiniifolia</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., 2014, VŽ	L4	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ericaceae	<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ericaceae	<i>Erica manipuliflora</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Dorycnium hirsutum</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Dorycnium pentaphyllum</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus coccifera</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus coccifera</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt. 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus ilex</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus robur</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt. 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	SERBIA, Paraćin, 06.05.2018, NV	L5	2
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus ornus*</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rhamnaceae	<i>Rhamnus lycioides</i> , ssp. <i>graeca</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus pumila</i>	GREECE, Pelion mt., 11.05.2016, VŽ	L2-5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L1-2	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac, 27.06.2015, SS	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 08.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma neustria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 18.07.2013, VŽ	L4	1
Lasiocampidae	<i>Trichiura crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Lycaenidae	<i>Callophrys rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Betulaceae	<i>Betula pendula</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 20.06.2016, SS	L5	-
Lycaenidae	<i>Polyommatus daphnis</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Fabaceae	<i>Securigera varia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Nepticulidae	<i>Ectoedemia argyropeza</i> (Zeller, 1839)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus alba</i>	SLOVENIA, Malečnik, 1989, JF	L5	-
Nepticulidae	<i>Ectoedemia argyropeza</i> (Zeller, 1839)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus nigra</i>	SLOVENIA, Maribor, Ajdovščina, 1989, JF	L5	-
Nepticulidae	<i>Ectoedemia argyropeza</i> (Zeller, 1839)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	SLOVENIA, Velenje, Ljubljana, 1989, JF	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta euphorbiae</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Pčinja canyon, 14.06.2014, VŽ	L4	-
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta euphorbiae</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex</i> sp.	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac, 1040 m a.s.l., 25.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta leporina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Užice, 02.08.2008, AP	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta rumicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Lamiaceae	<i>Mentha piperita</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 08.11.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta rumicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 08.10.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta rumicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rhamnaceae	<i>Frangula alnus</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta rumicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Stevan Sindjelić, 25.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta rumicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 01.08.2016, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Noctuidae	<i>Actinotia polyodon</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Clusiaceae	<i>Hypericum rumeliacum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrochola litura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Tara mt, 1000 m, 27.06.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Agrochola litura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Apiaceae	<i>Anthriscus caucalis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 20.05.2015, MIM	L4	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrochola lychnidis</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrochola lychnidis</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrotis exclamationis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 30.06.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrotis exclamationis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 09.11.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrotis segetum</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	Poaceae root	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 17.02.2019, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Agrotis segetum</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	Poaceae root	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 22.09.2018, VŽ	L4-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Allophytes oxyacanthae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus spinosa</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 13.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Ammoconia caecimacula</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Apiaceae	<i>Smyrnium perfoliatum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 16.05.2015, ML	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Ammoconia caecimacula</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Apiaceae	<i>Smyrnium perfoliatum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 21.05.2015, ML	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Amphipyra berbera</i> Rungs, 1949	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt (750m), 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Amphipyra pyramidea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oleaceae	<i>Syringa vulgaris</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 25.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Amphipyra pyramidea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix babylonica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Donja Vrežina, 14.04.2018, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Amphipyra tetra</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 01.08.2015, SS	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Amphipyra tragopoginis</i> (Clerck, 1759)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 21.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Amphipyra tragopoginis</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Asteraceae	<i>Crepis foetida</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Mediana, 25.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Anorthoa munda</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Pčinja canyon, 14.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Anorthoa munda</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Radan mt (750m), 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Anorthoa munda</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Asteroscopus sphinx</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus japonicus</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Asteroscopus sphinx</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Oleaceae	<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Autographa gamma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Stara Pazova 04.07.2013, BH	0	1
Noctuidae	<i>Calophasia lunula</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Plantaginaceae	<i>Linaria genistifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.05.2014, VŽ	L2, L4-5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Noctuidae	<i>Catocala fulminea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cerastis rubricosa</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Chrysodeixis chalcites</i> (Esper, 1789)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 25.09.2018, VŽ	L5, P	-
Noctuidae	<i>Conistra rubiginosa</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	/	/	SERBIA, Stara Pazova, 19.05.2017, BH	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Cosmia affinis</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cosmia affinis</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Craniophora ligustri</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Poaceae	/	SERBIA, Radan mt., 10.06.2017, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lanceolata</i> (Villers, 1789)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 16.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lanceolata</i> (Villers, 1789)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 16.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lanceolata</i> (Villers, 1789)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Pirot, Vlasi 23.07.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lucifuga</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 01.08.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lucifuga</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Asteraceae	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	AUSTRIA, Tirol, Oberburgl, 27.07.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lychnitis</i> (Rambur, 1833)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Tara, Derventa canyon, 25.06.2013, VŽ	L4	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia lychnitis</i> (Rambur, 1833)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum pulverulentum</i>	SERBIA, Zvonačka banja, 19.07.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia prenanthis</i> Boisduval, 1840	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m, 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia verbasci</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, VŽ	L2	1
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia verbasci</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Stara Pazova 13.05.2013, BH	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia verbasci</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., Derventa canyon, 25.06.2015, VŽ	L4-5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Cucullia verbasci</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac, 27.06.2015, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Dicycla oo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 11.05.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura, 14.05.2013, VŽ	L2	1
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 10.05.2015, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 14.05.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus spinosa</i>	GREECE, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Noctuidae	<i>Diloba caeruleocephala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 12.05.2015, VŽ	L4-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Enargia paleacea</i> (Esper, 1788)	Malvaceae	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L4	-
Noctuidae	<i>Eupsilia transversa</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Griposia aprilina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Hecatera bicolorata</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Asteraceae	<i>Hieracium</i> sp.	SERBIA, Radan mt., 12.06.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> (Hübner, 1808)	Geraniaceae	<i>Pelargonium zonale</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Trošarina 18.09.2018, VŽ	L4-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Heliothis peltigera</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac 27.06.2015, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Heliothis virespica</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea</i> sp.	CROATIA, Plitvice (lake), 22.06.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Mamestra oleracea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, Faculty of Agronomy, 09.2018, KK	P	1
Noctuidae	<i>Mesapamea secalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Mniotype satura</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Noctua pronuba</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cerasi</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix alba</i>	MONTENEGRO, Durmitor, Škrčko jezero (lake) 23.07.2003, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cerasi</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cerasi</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix fragilis</i>	CROATIA, Plitvice (lake), 29.06.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cerasi</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L3-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cerasi</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 20.05.2015, MIM	L3-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cruda</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L2-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cruda</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Iustiniana Prima, 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cruda</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L3-5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia cruda</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Malvaceae	<i>Tilia tomentosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gothica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Apiaceae	<i>Anthriscus caucalis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, MIM	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gothica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Betulaceae	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gothica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Geum aleppicum</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gothica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gracilis</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Viburnaceae	<i>Sambucus ebulus</i>	SERBIA, Brzi brod, 03.05.2018, VŽ	L4-5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gracilis</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Viburnaceae	<i>Sambucus ebulus</i>	SERBIA, Niška Banja, 24.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gracilis</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex sp.</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia gracilis</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Viburnaceae	<i>Sambucus ebulus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac 21.05.2017, SS	L4-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia incerta</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 04.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Orthosia miniosa</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium sp.?</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt, 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Phlogophora meticulosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Phlogophora meticulosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 09.03.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Phlogophora meticulosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Fragaria x ananassa</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, BF, 20.03.2019, ŠM	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Rileyiana fovea</i> (Treitschke, 1825)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Scoliopteryx libatrix</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Stara planina mt. (1200 m), 02.08.2018, VŽ	L3-5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Simyra albovovosa</i> (Goeze, 1781)	Poaceae	<i>Phalaroides arundinacea</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park, 06.06.2018, DM	L5	1
Noctuidae	<i>Thalophila matura</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	/	Poaceae root	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 17.02.2019, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Xylena exsoleta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., Derventa canyon, 27.06.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Noctuidae	<i>Xylena lunifera</i> Warren, 1910	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex sp.</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 13.05.2015, VŽ	L5, P	-
Notodontidae	<i>Cerura erminea</i> (Esper, 1783)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 11.07.2013, VŽ	L2, L4-5	1
Notodontidae	<i>Cerura vinula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 11.07.2013, VŽ	L4-5	1
Notodontidae	<i>Cerura vinula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix amplexicaulis</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 15.07.2010, VŽ	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Notodonta ziczac</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m a.s.l., 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Ptilodon capucina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	AUSTRIA, Tirol, Obergurgl, 27.07.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Ptilodon capucina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 01.08.2015, VŽ	L4	-
Notodontidae	<i>Ptilophora plumigera</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 12.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Ptilophora plumigera</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 15.05.2018, SS	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Ptilophora plumigera</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	SERBIA, Sicevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Ptilophora plumigera</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	SERBIA, Kopaonik mt., 19.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Thaumetopoea pityocampa</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	/	/	GREECE, Athens, Botanical Garden, 06.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Notodontidae	<i>Thaumetopoea pityocampa</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Pinaceae	<i>Pinus nigra</i>	BOSNIA, AND HERZEGOVINA, Tula 17.03.2018, DD	L4-5, P	1
Notodontidae	<i>Thaumetopoea processionea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 23.05.2014, MIM	L5	-
Notodontidae	<i>Thaumetopoea solitaria</i> (Freyer, 1838)	Anacardiaceae	<i>Pistacia terebinthus</i>	GREECE, Attica, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L5, P	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Stara planina, Rosomača, 02.08.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 10.06.2017, SS	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Stara planina (mt.), Rosomača 02.08.2018, VŽ	L4	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	MONTENEGRO, Plavsko jezero, Gusinje, 12.07.2013, VŽ	L4-5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	AUSTRIA, Tirol, Obergurgl, 27.07.2015, VŽ	L4	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	BULGARIA, Rila mt. 7 lakes, 23.07.2017, VŽ	L4-5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	BULGARIA, Rila mt. Skakavitsa, 20.07.2019, VŽ	L4-5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	BULGARIA, Rila mt. Malyovitsa, 21.07.2019, VŽ	L2	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	MONTENEGRO, Durmitor, Ledena pečina, 17.07.2016, SS	L4-5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), Čemernik, 15.09.2017, VŽ	L2	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	POLAND, Kampinos National Park 06.06.2018, VŽ	L2	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Boloria titania</i> (Esper, 1793)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Kopaonik mt., 19.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Brenthis daphne</i> (Bergsträsser, 1780)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus caesius</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Brenthis ino</i> (Bergsträsser, 1780)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Melanargia galathea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Poaceae	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 10.05.2017, VŽ	L4	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea arduinna</i> (Esper, 1783)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 18.06.2014, VŽ	L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea arduinna</i> (Esper, 1783)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea arduinna</i> (Esper, 1783)	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.?	SERBIA, Radan mt, 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea athalia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Orobanchaceae	<i>Melampyrum pratense</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 19.05.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea athalia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolatum</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea aurelia</i> Nickerl, 1850	Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	SERBIA, Kopaonik mt., 19.06.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea diamina</i> (Lang, 1789)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 15.06.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea diamina</i> (Lang, 1789)	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Dianthus carthusianorum</i> *	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., 27.06.2013, VŽ	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea diamina</i> (Lang, 1789)	Rosaceae	<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 16.06.2013, VŽ	L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, 1778)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, 1778)	Orobanchaceae	<i>Melampyrum arvense</i>	SERBIA, Sićevaka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L3-4	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, 1778)	Plantaginaceae	<i>Linaria dalmatica</i> , ssp. <i>macedonica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 25.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, 1778)	Plantaginaceae	<i>Linaria</i> sp.	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 11.07.2013 ŽT	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, 1778)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum</i> sp.	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 16.06.2013, VŽ	L2, L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea phoebe</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 16.06.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea phoebe</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea rhenana</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 18.06.2014, VŽ	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea trivia</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum</i> sp.	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 21.04.2018, VŽ	L3	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea trivia</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Dukat mt., 1000 m a.s.l. 07.08.2011, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea trivia</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Jerma canyon, Vlasi, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea trivia</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 08.06.2014, VŽ	L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea trivia</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 16.06.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea trivia</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 25.08.2017, VŽ	L2	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m. a.s.l., 11.07.2013, AP	L5	2
Nymphalidae	<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 1000 m. a.s.l., 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Sićevaka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 19.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 750 m 10.05.2018, VŽ	L4-5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	GREECE, Komotini, 12.05.2002, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Plužine 08.07.2013, AP & VŽ	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Polygona c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Stara planina mt. (1200 m), 02.08.2018, VŽ	L4-5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Polygona c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero 06.08.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Polygona c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero, 06.08.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Polygona c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Kopaonik, Metode, 18.07.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Vanessa atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Stara Pazova, 06.2013, BH	L5	1
Nymphalidae	<i>Vanessa atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	SERBIA, Stara planina, Tupavica 02.08.2018, VŽ	L3-4	-
Nymphalidae	<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asteraceae	<i>Carlina acanthifolia</i>	SERBIA, Dukat mt., Jarešnik, 1230 m a.s.l., 23.07.2013, VŽ	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Nymphalidae	<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt. 13.07.2013, AP	L5	1
Papilionidae	<i>Zerynthia cerisyi</i> Godart, 1824	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia clematitis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 20.06.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Papilionidae	<i>Zerynthia cerisyi</i> Godart, 1824	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia clematitis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Popovac, 14.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Papilionidae	<i>Papilio machaon</i> Linnaeus, 1757	Apiaceae	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura, 16.07.2013, SS	L5	1
Papilionidae	<i>Papilio machaon</i> Linnaeus, 1758	/	/	AUSTRIA, Tirol, Obergurgl, 24.07.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Papilionidae	<i>Papilio machaon</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Apiaceae	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura 16.06.2009, VŽ	L5	1
Papilionidae	<i>Zerynthia cerisy</i> (Godart, 1824)	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia clematitis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.07.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Papilionidae	<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia clematitis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Mediana, 11.06.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Papilionidae	<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i> (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia clematitis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Popovac, 09.06.2010, VŽ	L5	-
Pieridae	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Brassicaceae	<i>Alliaria petiolata</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 19.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura (gorge), 14.05.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), Ostrovica, 28.05.2013, VŽ	L3	-
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 16.06.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 09.05.2015, VŽ	L5	1
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.05.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Jadovnik, Sopotnica, 01.06.2014, PJ	L5	1
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L2-5	-
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, SST	L4	1
Pieridae	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., Derventa canyon, 25.06.2015, VŽ	L4	-
Pieridae	<i>Pieris brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Stara Pazova, 30.08.2013, BH	L5	1
Pieridae	<i>Pieris brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i>	SLOVENIA, Zgornja Lipnica, 15.07.2014, ST, TB & MV	L5	1
Pieridae	<i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 20.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Pieridae	<i>Pieris rapae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 01.07.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Pieridae	<i>Pieris rapae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SPAIN, Fuerteventura, 01.04.2017, YML	L5	1
Plutellidae	<i>Plutella xylostella</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica napus</i>	SERBIA, SERBIAobran, 20.05.2018, MP	L4-5	1
Plutellidae	<i>Plutella xylostella</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, 2014, TB	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Praydidae	<i>Prays citri</i> (Millière)	Rutaceae	<i>Citrus x sinensis</i>	GREECE, Thessaloniki, 15.07.2002, NK	L5	1
Praydidae	<i>Prays oleae</i> (Bernard, 1788)	Oleaceae	<i>Olea europaea</i>	GREECE, Crete, Messara, 09-16.06.2017, NK	L5	6
Psychidae	<i>Acanthopsyche atra</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	/	/	SERBIA, Radan mt. (750 m), 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Psychidae	<i>Acanthopsycheatra</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Poaceae	<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 12.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Canephora hirsuta</i> (Poda, 1761)	/	/	SERBIA, Valjevo, Počuta, 17.05.2013, AP	L5	1
Psychidae	<i>Dahlia</i> sp.	/	/	GREECE, Gramos mt., 1900 m, 17.07.2003, NK	L5	1
Psychidae	<i>Megalophanes viciella</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Betulaceae	<i>Betula pubescens</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 16.06.2009, VŽ	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Megalophanes viciella</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Ericaceae	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 19.06.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Psychidae	<i>Megalophanes viciella</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia villosa</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 12.06.2016, VŽ	L5	3
Psychidae	<i>Megalophanes viciella</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Poaceae*	/	GREECE, Peloponessus, Xerocampos, Nemea 24.05.2016, AN	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Megalophanes viciella</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Poaceae*	/	SERBIA, Pantelej, 11.08.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Pachythelia villosella</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1810)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleagnifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Psyche casta</i> (Pallas, 1767)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 02.06.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Psychidae	<i>Psyche casta</i> (Pallas, 1767)	Poaceae*	/	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 31.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Rebellia sapho</i> (Millière, 1864)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 09.09.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Taleporia tubulosa</i> (Retzius, 1783)	/	/	SERBIA, Radan mt. 1000 m. 12.06.2016, SS	L5	-
Psychidae	<i>Teleporia</i> sp.	Malvaceae	<i>Tilia x europaea</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 13.05.2018, VŽ	L4	-
Pterophoridae	<i>Adaina microdactyla</i> (Hübner 1813)	Asteraceae	<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i>	SLOVENIA, Ivanjковci, Piran, 1989 JF	L5	-
Pterophoridae	<i>Emmelina monodactyla</i> cf. (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Stara Pazova 30.08.2013, BH	L5	1
Pterophoridae	<i>Pterophorus pentadactyla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja 24.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Pyralidae	<i>Galleria mellonella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	bee hive	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, BF, 01.06.2018, KK	L5	1
Pyralidae	<i>Plodia interpunctella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Juglandaceae	<i>Juglans regia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 23.08.20008, VŽ	L4-5	1
Pyralidae	<i>Acrobasis consociella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus cerris</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac 26.04.2018, ML	L5	-
Saturniidae	<i>Aglia tau</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Tara mt., Derventa canyon, 25.06.2015, VŽ	L4	-
Saturniidae	<i>Aglia tau</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SPAIN, Montenegro de Cameros, Soria, 01.04.2017, OM	L5	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	MONTENEGRO, Cetinje, 09.07.2013, VŽ	L3-5	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	/	/	SERBIA, Tara mt., 25.06.2015, VŽ	L4-5	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L2-3	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L3	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Rosaceae	<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L3	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus minor</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 11.05.2017, VŽ	L2-3	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus minor</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), 15.05.2013, VŽ	L2-3	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia pavoniella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L2-3	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia</i> sp.	/	/	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 19.05.2018, VŽ	L2-4	-
Saturniidae	<i>Saturnia</i> sp.	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Brzi brod, 03.05.2018, VŽ	L1	-
Sesiidae	<i>Bembecia ichneumoniformis</i> (Schiffmüller & Denis, 1776)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Vipava, 07.05.2000, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Bembecia magillaeformis</i> (Hübner, 1813)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Dragonja, 02.06.2002, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Bembecia pavicevici</i> (Toševski, 1989)	Fabaceae	<i>Hippocrepis emerus</i>	SLOVENIA, Kraški rob, 02.05.2003, ŽP & H-PT	L5	-
Sesiidae	<i>Bembecia scopigera</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Kozina, 27.05.2005, ŽP & H-PT	L5	-
Sesiidae	<i>Chamaesphacia empiformis</i> (Esper, 1783)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Velenje, 20.09.2002, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Pyropteron affinis</i> (Staudinger, 1856)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Kozina, 04.04.2000, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Pyropteron chrysidiformis</i> (Esper, 1782)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Vipava, 07.05.2000, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon cephaliformis</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Vrhnika, 03.04.2004, ŽP & H-PT	L5	-
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon culiciformis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Podvin pri Polzei, 20.12.1999, ŽP & H-PT	L5	-
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon formicaeformis</i> (Esper, 1783) (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Raduha, 02.06.2003, ŽP & H-PT	L5	-
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon loranthi</i> (Kraliček, 1966)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Maribor, 21.04.2005, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon melliniformis</i> (Laspeyres, 1801)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Gradišče, 08.06.2000, ŽP & H-PT	L5	1
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon tipuliformis</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Grossulariaceae	<i>Ribes nigrum</i>	SLOVENIA, all Slovenia, 1989, JF	L5	-
Sesiidae	<i>Synanthedon vespiformis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	/	/	SLOVENIA, Galicija, 14.02.2001, ŽP & H-PT	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Sphingidae	<i>Agrius convolvuli</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 13.10.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Sphingidae	<i>Agrius convolvuli</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 13.10.2014, VŽ	L5	-
Sphingidae	<i>Deilephila elpenor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 25.08.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Sphingidae	<i>Deilephila porcellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rubiaceae	<i>Galium album</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor, Čavlovac, 28.06.2018, ML	L5	-
Sphingidae	<i>Hyles euphorbiae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 18.06.2017, SS	L5	-
Sphingidae	<i>Mimas tiliae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 16.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Sphingidae	<i>Mimas tiliae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	UNITED KINGDOM, London, Finchley, 13.07.2018, NKD	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Aphelia paleana</i> (Hübner, 1793)	/	/	MONTENEGRO, Visitor, 11.07.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Aphelia viburnana</i> (Denis and Schiffermüller, 1775)	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips crataeganus</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Fagaceae	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt 750 m, 10.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Erebidae	<i>Archips podana</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 25.05.2016, VŽ	L4-5	2
Tortricidae	<i>Archips podana</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Malvaceae	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 25.05.2016, VŽ	L4-5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips podana</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 12.06.2016, VŽ	L4-5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips podana</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 31.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	/	/	SERBIA, Niš, Pailula, 09.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera nigra</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 14.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, MIM	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 24.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 14.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Corylaceae	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Geraniaceae	<i>Geranium robertianum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 15.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Geraniaceae	<i>Geranium</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Grossulariaceae	<i>Ribes nigrum</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Grossulariaceae	<i>Ribes rubrum</i>	SERBIA, Kruševac, Donji Stepoš, 01.05.2018, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Juglandaceae	<i>Juglans regia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oleaceae	<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 04.05.2017, SS	L5	2
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	POLAND, Kampinos Nat. Park Sieraków, 04.06.2018, DM	L5	2
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 14.05.2017, VŽ	L5	2
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	2
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	2
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Malvaceae	<i>Tilia</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 24.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura, 14.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Palilula, 09.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, Sićevo, 11.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Kamenički vis, 15.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Kruševac, Donji Stepoš, 01.08.2018, ML	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Kruševac, Donji Stepoš, 06.05.2016, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Vinik, 09.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, SS	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 15.05.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, Ostrovica, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 13.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, SS	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L4-5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	SERBIA, Siće vačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus eleanifolia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus discolor</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, Sićevo, 25.05.2018, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus ideaus</i>	SLOVENIA, Ljubljana, BF, 20.7.2018, ŠM	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 24.05.2018, SS	L4-5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix amplexicaulis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix amplexicaulis</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Sapindaceae	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Kamenički vis, 02.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 20.05.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 14.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips rosanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 17.04.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips xylosteanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt 1000 m, 12.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips xylosteanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa canina</i>	SERBIA, Prokuplje, Gornja Konjuša, 01.06.2016, MR	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Archips xylosteanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus tremula</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt 1000 m, 10.06.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Archips xylosteanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 17.04.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Cydia pomonella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SPAIN, Asturias, 01.05.2015, MM	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia festivana</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	SLOVENIA, Šmarje pri Jelšah, 1989, JF	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia festivana</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	SLOVENIA, Strunjan, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia festivana</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus robur</i>	SLOVENIA, Gornji Grad, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia nisella</i> (Clerck, 1759)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus alba</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 12.05.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia tetraquetra</i> (Haworth, 1811)	Betulaceae	<i>Alnus incana</i>	SLOVENIA, Planina pod Golico, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Epinotia tetraquetra</i> (Haworth, 1811)	Betulaceae	<i>Betula pendula</i>	SLOVENIA, Benedikt, Grgar, 1989, JF	L5	-

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Tortricidae	<i>Eudemis profundana</i> (Denis and Schiffmüller, 1775)	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Gypsonoma aceriana</i> (Dufrane 1945)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus euroamericana</i>	SLOVENIA, Dobrovo v Goriških Brdih, 1989, JF	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Gypsonoma aceriana</i> (Dufrane 1945)	Salicaceae	<i>Populus nigra</i>	SLOVENIA, Solkan, Dekani, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Cornaceae	<i>Cornus mas</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, MIM	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 22.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Jelašnička klisura, 14.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Kravljice, 22.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 22.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	SERBIA, Kruševac, Donji Stepoš, 16.04.2016, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 22.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya nubiferana</i> (Haworth, [1811])	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya pruniana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya pruniana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	GREECE, Athens, Tatoi, 07.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya pruniana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Hedya pruniana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Oblačinsko jezero, 19.04.2018, SS	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Neosphaloptera nubilana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Kamenički vis, 15.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Neosphaloptera nubilana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Neosphaloptera nubilana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 22.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Notocelia aquana</i> (Hübner, [1796-1999])	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, MIM	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Notocelia uddmanniana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Geum aleppicum</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura, Gradište, 07.05.2018, SS	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Notocelia uddmanniana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura, 11.05.2017, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Notocelia uddmanniana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	SERBIA, Sopot, Guberevac, 24.05.2014, BH	L6	1

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Tortricidae	<i>Notocelia uddmanniana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Spiraea douglasii</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake) 15.05.2016, MIM	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Olindia schumacherana</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	/	/	SERBIA, Suva planina, Bojanine vode, 25.05.2018, ML	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Orthotaenia undulana</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 26.04.2018, ML	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Pandemis cerasana</i> (Hübner, 1786)	Salicaceae	<i>Salix caprea</i>	SERBIA, Stara planina, Tupavica 02.08.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Retinia resinella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Pinaceae	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	SLOVENIA, Rakek, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Ptycholoma lecheana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	SERBIA, Banja Topilo, 22.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Rhopobota naevana</i> (Hübner, 1817)	Rosaceae	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, 12.05.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Rhyacionia buoliana</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Pinaceae	<i>Pinus mugo</i> , <i>P. nigra</i>	SLOVENIA, Subalpine belt, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Rhyacionia buoliana</i> (Denis & Schiffmüller, 1775)	Pinaceae	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	SLOVENIA, Subalpine belt, 1989, JF	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Syricoris siderana</i> (Treitschke, 1835)	Rosaceae	<i>Spiraea</i> sp.	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 22.05.2016, VŽ	L4-5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Tortrix viridana</i> Linnaeus, 1757	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	GREECE, Magnesia, Almyros, 11.05.2016, SS	L4-5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Tortrix viridana</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero, 27.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Tortricidae	<i>Tortrix viridana</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Fagaceae	<i>Quercus frainetto</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Delijski vis, 23.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Tortrix viridana</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Oleaceae	<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 24.04.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Tortrix viridana</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 24.04.2018, SS	L4-5	-
Tortricidae	<i>Tortrix viridana</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i>	SERBIA, Sićevačka klisura, Ostrovica, 01.05.2018, VŽ	L5	1
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta cagnagella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus europaeus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 22.05.2013, VŽ	L4-5	3
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta cagnagella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus verrucosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška banja, 11.06.2015, VŽ	L5	4
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta cagnagella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus verucosa</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 13.05.2015, VŽ	L5	4
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta cagnagella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus europaeus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 13.05.2015, VŽ	L4-5	2
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta cagnagella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus japonicus</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Niška Banja, 14.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	2
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta cagnagella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Celastraceae	<i>Euonymus europaeus</i>	SERBIA, Lebane, Iustiniana Prima, 01.05.2017, VŽ	L4-5	2
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta evonymella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus padus</i>	AUSTRIA, Tirol, Obergurgl, 27.07.2015, VŽ	P	2

Table A1 – continued

Lepidopteran family	Lepidopteran species	Host plant / food family	Host plant / food species	Locality, date, and legator	Stage/index	No sp.
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta evonymella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus padus</i>	SWEDEN, Uppsala, 03.07.2014, VŽ	P	2
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta malinellus</i> (Zeller, 1838)	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt. 10.06.2015, SS	L5, P	5
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta padella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt. 10.06.2016, SS	L5, P	5
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta padella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 25.05.2015, VŽ	P	2
Yponomeutidae	<i>Yponomeuta padella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus persica</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Vinik, 12.05.2015, VŽ	L5	2
Zygaenidae	<i>Jordanita</i> sp.	/	/	Spain, Sevilla, Aznalcázar, 03.05.2017, YML	A	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena camiolica</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	/	/	SERBIA, Zlatibor, Čavlovac 28.06.2018, ML	L5, P	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena camiolica</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Fabaceae	<i>Onobrychis vicifolia</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 19.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena camiolica</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Fabaceae	<i>Onobrychis vicifolia</i>	SERBIA, Tara mt., Derventa canyon, 25.06.2017, VŽ	L5	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ephialtes</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Fabaceae	<i>Astragalus vesicaria</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L4	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ephialtes</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Fabaceae	<i>Securigera varia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ephialtes</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Fabaceae	<i>Securigera varia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Pantelej, 11.05.2015, VŽ	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 10.05.2012, VŽ	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), 15.07.2013, VŽ	L5	8
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	SERBIA, Vlasinsko jezero (lake), 16.06.2012, SS	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Astragalus onobrychis</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 25.05.2015, VŽ	L5	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Astragalus vesicaria</i>	SERBIA, Sičevačka klisura (gorge), Gradište, 07.05.2018, VŽ	L5	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia grandiflora</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 25.05.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena filipendulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia grandiflora</i>	SERBIA, Radan mt., 12.06.2016, VŽ	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ionicerae</i> (Scheven, 1777)	Dipsacaceae	<i>Knautia arvensis</i>	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 13.07.2013, VŽ	L5	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ionicerae</i> (Scheven, 1777)	Dipsacaceae	<i>Knautia arvensis</i>	SERBIA, Zlatibor mt., Čavlovac, 27.06.2013, SS	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ionicerae</i> (Scheven, 1777)	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	SERBIA, Kopaonik mt., 19.06.2016, VŽ	L5	-
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ionicerae</i> (Scheven)	Fabaceae	<i>Lotus tetragonolobus</i>	GREECE, Peloponessus, Xerocampos, Nemea 24.05.2016, AN	L5	2
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena ionicerae</i> (Scheven, 1777)	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.	MONTENEGRO, Visitor mt., 11.07.2013, VŽ	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena purpuralis</i> (Brünnich, 1763)	Lamiaceae	<i>Thymus serpyllum</i>	SERBIA, Jadovnik, 10.06.2015, PJ	L5	1
Zygaenidae	<i>Zygaena</i> sp.	Fabaceae	<i>Securigera varia</i>	SERBIA, Niš, Gornji Matejevac, 21.05.2017, SS	L5	-